
INFINITE DIMENSIONAL GHOBBER-JAMING UNCERTAINTY PRINCIPLE

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Abstract: By extending the notion of p-orthonormal basis from finite to infinite dimensional Banach spaces, we show that finite dimensional functional Ghobber-Jaming uncertainty principle can be extended to infinite dimensions.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Motivated from the Nazarov-Jaming uncertainty principle [3,4,6] and from the Donoho-Stark uncertainty principles [1], in 2011, Ghobber and Jaming [2] derived the following beautiful theorem. In the paper, given a subset $M \subseteq \mathbb{N}$, the number of elements in M is denoted by $o(M)$.

Theorem 1.1. [2] (*Ghobber-Jaming Uncertainty Principle*) Let $\{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^n$ and $\{\omega_j\}_{j=1}^n$ be orthonormal bases for the Hilbert space \mathbb{C}^n . If $M, N \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\}$ are such that

$$o(M)o(N) < \frac{1}{\max_{1 \leq j, k \leq n} |\langle \tau_j, \omega_k \rangle|^2},$$

then for all $h \in \mathbb{C}^n$,

$$\|h\| \leq \left(1 + \frac{1}{1 - \sqrt{o(M)o(N)} \max_{1 \leq j, k \leq n} |\langle \tau_j, \omega_k \rangle|} \right) \left[\left(\sum_{j \in M^c} |\langle h, \tau_j \rangle|^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} + \left(\sum_{k \in N^c} |\langle h, \omega_k \rangle|^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right].$$

In particular, if h is supported on M in the expansion using basis $\{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^n$ and h is supported on N in the expansion using basis $\{\omega_j\}_{j=1}^n$, then $h = 0$.

In a recent paper, Banach space version of Theorem 1.1 has been obtained with the introduction of p-orthonormal basis.

Definition 1.2. [5] Let \mathcal{X} be a finite dimensional Banach space over \mathbb{K} . Let $\{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^n$ be a basis for \mathcal{X} and let $\{f_j\}_{j=1}^n$ be the coordinate functionals associated with $\{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^n$. The pair $(\{f_j\}_{j=1}^n, \{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^n)$ is said to be a **p-orthonormal basis** ($1 < p < \infty$) for \mathcal{X} if the following conditions hold.

- (i) $\|f_j\| = \|\tau_j\| = 1$ for all $1 \leq j \leq n$.
- (ii) For every $(a_j)_{j=1}^n \in \mathbb{K}^n$,

$$\left\| \sum_{j=1}^n a_j \tau_j \right\| = \left(\sum_{j=1}^n |a_j|^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}.$$

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Theorem 1.3. [5] (*Functional Ghobber-Jaming Uncertainty Principle*) Let $(\{f_j\}_{j=1}^n, \{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^n)$ and $(\{g_k\}_{k=1}^n, \{\omega_k\}_{k=1}^n)$ be p -orthonormal bases for \mathcal{X} . If $M, N \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\}$ are such that

$$o(M)^{\frac{1}{q}} o(N)^{\frac{1}{p}} < \frac{1}{\max_{1 \leq j, k \leq n} |g_k(\tau_j)|},$$

then for all $x \in \mathcal{X}$,

$$\|x\| \leq \left(1 + \frac{1}{1 - o(M)^{\frac{1}{q}} o(N)^{\frac{1}{p}} \max_{1 \leq j, k \leq n} |g_k(\tau_j)|} \right) \left[\left(\sum_{j \in M^c} |f_j(x)|^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} + \left(\sum_{k \in N^c} |g_k(x)|^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \right].$$

In particular, if x is supported on M in the expansion using basis $\{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^n$ and x is supported on N in the expansion using basis $\{\omega_k\}_{k=1}^n$, then $x = 0$.

In this article, we show that by extending the definition of p -orthonormal basis for a class of Schauder frames, we can derive infinite dimensional version of Theorem 1.3.

2. INFINITE DIMENSIONAL GHOBBER-JAMING UNCERTAINTY PRINCIPLE

In the paper, \mathcal{X} denotes a Banach space over \mathbb{K} (\mathbb{R} or \mathbb{C}). We denote the identity operator on \mathcal{X} by $I_{\mathcal{X}}$. Dual of \mathcal{X} is denoted by \mathcal{X}^* . Whenever $1 < p < \infty$, q denotes conjugate index of p . Canonical basis for $\ell^p(\mathbb{N})$ is denoted by $\{\delta_j\}_{j=1}^{\infty}$ and $\{\zeta_j\}_{j=1}^{\infty}$ denotes the coordinate functionals associated with $\{\delta_j\}_{j=1}^{\infty}$. We need the following infinite generalization of Definition 1.2.

Definition 2.1. Let \mathcal{X} be a Banach space which admits an unconditional Schauder basis $\{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^{\infty}$. Let $\{f_j\}_{j=1}^{\infty}$ be the coordinate functionals associated with $\{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^{\infty}$. The pair $(\{f_j\}_{j=1}^{\infty}, \{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^{\infty})$ is said to be a **p -orthonormal basis** ($1 < p < \infty$) for \mathcal{X} if the following conditions hold.

- (i) $\|f_j\| = \|\tau_j\| = 1$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$.
- (ii) For every $x \in \mathcal{X}$, $\{f_j(x)\}_{j=1}^{\infty} \in \ell^p(\mathbb{N})$.
- (iii) For every $\{a_j\}_{j=1}^{\infty} \in \ell^p(\mathbb{N})$, $\sum_{j=1}^{\infty} a_j \tau_j$ converges in \mathcal{X} and

$$\left\| \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} a_j \tau_j \right\| = \left(\sum_{j=1}^{\infty} |a_j|^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}.$$

Given a p -orthonormal basis $(\{f_j\}_{j=1}^{\infty}, \{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^{\infty})$, we see from Definition 2.1 that

$$\|x\| = \left\| \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} f_j(x) \tau_j \right\| = \left(\sum_{j=1}^{\infty} |f_j(x)|^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}, \quad \forall x \in \mathcal{X}.$$

Example 2.2. The pair $(\{\zeta_j\}_{j=1}^{\infty}, \{\delta_j\}_{j=1}^{\infty})$ is a p -orthonormal basis for $\ell^p(\mathbb{N})$.

We characterizes all p -orthonormal bases.

Theorem 2.3. Let $(\{f_j\}_{j=1}^{\infty}, \{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^{\infty})$ be a p -orthonormal basis for \mathcal{X} . Then a pair $(\{g_j\}_{j=1}^{\infty}, \{\omega_j\}_{j=1}^{\infty})$ is a p -orthonormal basis for \mathcal{X} if and only if there is an invertible linear isometry $V : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{X}$ such that

$$g_j = f_j V^{-1}, \quad \omega_j = V \tau_j, \quad \forall j \in \mathbb{N}.$$

Proof. (\Rightarrow) Define $V : \mathcal{X} \ni x \mapsto \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} f_j(x)\omega_j \in \mathcal{X}$. Since $\{\omega_j\}_{j=1}^{\infty}$ is a Schauder basis for \mathcal{X} , V is invertible with inverse $V^{-1} : \mathcal{X} \ni x \mapsto \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} g_j(x)\tau_j \in \mathcal{X}$. For $x \in \mathcal{X}$,

$$\|Vx\| = \left\| \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} f_j(x)\omega_j \right\| = \left(\sum_{j=1}^{\infty} |f_j(x)|^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} = \left\| \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} f_j(x)\tau_j \right\| = \|x\|.$$

Therefore V is isometry. We clearly have $\omega_j = V\tau_j, \forall j \in \mathbb{N}$. Now let $j \in \mathbb{N}$. Then

$$f_j(V^{-1}x) = f_j \left(\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} g_k(x)\tau_k \right) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} g_k(x)f_j(\tau_k) = g_j(x), \quad \forall x \in \mathcal{X}.$$

(\Leftarrow) Since V is invertible, $\{\omega_j\}_{j=1}^{\infty}$ is an unconditional Schauder basis for \mathcal{X} . Now we see that $g_j(\omega_k) = f_j(V^{-1}V\tau_k) = f_j(\tau_k) = \delta_{j,k}$ for all $j, k \in \mathbb{N}$. Therefore $\{g_j\}_{j=1}^{\infty}$ is the coordinate functionals associated with $\{\omega_j\}_{j=1}^{\infty}$. Since V is an isometry, we have $\|\omega_j\| = 1$ for all $j \in \mathbb{N}$. Since V is also invertible, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \|g_j\| &= \sup_{x \in \mathcal{X}, \|x\| \leq 1} |g_j(x)| = \sup_{x \in \mathcal{X}, \|x\| \leq 1} |f_j(V^{-1}x)| = \sup_{Vy \in \mathcal{X}, \|Vy\| \leq 1} |f_j(y)| \\ &= \sup_{Vy \in \mathcal{X}, \|y\| \leq 1} |f_j(y)| = \|f_j\| = 1, \quad \forall j \in \mathbb{N}. \end{aligned}$$

Let $\{a_j\}_{j=1}^{\infty} \in \ell^p(\mathbb{N})$. Then

$$\left\| \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} a_j \omega_j \right\| = \left\| \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} a_j V\tau_j \right\| = \left\| V \left(\sum_{j=1}^{\infty} a_j \tau_j \right) \right\| = \left\| \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} a_j \tau_j \right\| = \left(\sum_{j=1}^{\infty} |a_j|^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}.$$

□

Theorem 2.4. *If \mathcal{X} has a p -orthonormal basis $(\{f_j\}_{j=1}^{\infty}, \{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^{\infty})$, then \mathcal{X} is isometrically isomorphic to $\ell^p(\mathbb{N})$.*

Proof. Define $V : \mathcal{X} \ni x \mapsto \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} f_j(x)\delta_j \in \ell^p(\mathbb{N})$. Then V is an invertible isometry. □

Now we derive infinite dimensional version of Theorem 1.3.

Theorem 2.5. (Infinite dimensional Ghobber-Jaming Uncertainty Principle) *Let $(\{f_j\}_{j=1}^{\infty}, \{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^{\infty})$ and $(\{g_k\}_{k=1}^{\infty}, \{\omega_k\}_{k=1}^{\infty})$ be p -orthonormal bases for \mathcal{X} . If $M, N \subseteq \mathbb{N}$ are such that*

$$o(M)^{\frac{1}{q}} o(N)^{\frac{1}{p}} < \frac{1}{\sup_{j,k \in \mathbb{N}} |g_k(\tau_j)|},$$

then for all $x \in \mathcal{X}$,

$$(1) \quad \|x\| \leq \left(1 + \frac{1}{1 - o(M)^{\frac{1}{q}} o(N)^{\frac{1}{p}} \sup_{j,k \in \mathbb{N}} |g_k(\tau_j)|} \right) \left[\left(\sum_{j \in M^c} |f_j(x)|^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} + \left(\sum_{k \in N^c} |g_k(x)|^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \right].$$

In particular, if x is supported on M in the expansion using Schauder basis $\{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^{\infty}$ and x is supported on N in the expansion using Schauder basis $\{\omega_k\}_{k=1}^{\infty}$, then $x = 0$.

Proof. Given $S \subseteq \mathbb{N}$, define

$$P_S x := \sum_{j \in S} f_j(x)\tau_j, \quad \forall x \in \mathcal{X}, \quad \|x\|_{S,f} := \left(\sum_{j \in S} |f_j(x)|^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}, \quad \|x\|_{S,g} := \left(\sum_{j \in S} |g_j(x)|^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}.$$

Also define $V : \mathcal{X} \ni x \mapsto \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} g_k(x)\tau_k \in \mathcal{X}$. Then V is an invertible isometry. Using V we make following calculations:

$$\|P_S x\| = \left\| \sum_{j \in S} f_j(x)\tau_j \right\| = \left(\sum_{j \in S} |f_j(x)|^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} = \|x\|_{S,f}, \quad \forall x \in \mathcal{X}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \|P_S Vx\| &= \left\| \sum_{j \in S} f_j(Vx)\tau_j \right\| = \left\| \sum_{j \in S} f_j \left(\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} g_k(x)\tau_k \right) \tau_j \right\| = \left\| \sum_{j \in S} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} g_k(x) f_j(\tau_k) \tau_j \right\| \\ &= \left\| \sum_{j \in S} g_j(x)\tau_j \right\| = \left(\sum_{j \in S} |g_j(x)|^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} = \|x\|_{S,g}, \quad \forall x \in \mathcal{X}. \end{aligned}$$

Now let $y \in \mathcal{X}$ be such that $\{j \in \mathbb{N} : f_j(y) \neq 0\} \subseteq M$. Then $\|P_N V y\| = \|P_N V P_M y\| \leq \|P_N V P_M\| \|y\|$ and

$$\|y\|_{N^c,g} = \|P_{N^c} V y\| = \|V y - P_N V y\| \geq \|V y\| - \|P_N V y\| = \|y\| - \|P_N V y\| \geq \|y\| - \|P_N V P_M\| \|y\|.$$

Therefore

$$(2) \quad \|y\|_{N^c,g} \geq (1 - \|P_N V P_M\|) \|y\|.$$

Let $x \in \mathcal{X}$. Then $P_M x$ satisfies $\{j \in \mathbb{N} : f_j(P_M x) \neq 0\} \subseteq M$. Now using (2) we get

$$\begin{aligned} \|x\| &= \|P_M x + P_{M^c} x\| \leq \|P_M x\| + \|P_{M^c} x\| \leq \frac{1}{1 - \|P_N V P_M\|} \|P_M x\|_{N^c,g} + \|P_{M^c} x\| \\ &= \frac{1}{1 - \|P_N V P_M\|} \|P_{N^c} V P_M x\| + \|P_{M^c} x\| = \frac{1}{1 - \|P_N V P_M\|} \|P_{N^c} V(x - P_{M^c} x)\| + \|P_{M^c} x\| \\ &\leq \frac{1}{1 - \|P_N V P_M\|} \|P_{N^c} V x\| + \frac{1}{1 - \|P_N V P_M\|} \|P_{N^c} V P_{M^c} x\| + \|P_{M^c} x\| \\ &\leq \frac{1}{1 - \|P_N V P_M\|} \|P_{N^c} V x\| + \frac{1}{1 - \|P_N V P_M\|} \|P_{M^c} x\| + \|P_{M^c} x\| \\ &= \frac{1}{1 - \|P_N V P_M\|} \|P_{N^c} V x\| + \left(1 + \frac{1}{1 - \|P_N V P_M\|}\right) \|P_{M^c} x\| \\ &\leq \|P_{N^c} V x\| + \frac{1}{1 - \|P_N V P_M\|} \|P_{N^c} V x\| + \left(1 + \frac{1}{1 - \|P_N V P_M\|}\right) \|P_{M^c} x\| \\ &= \left(1 + \frac{1}{1 - \|P_N V P_M\|}\right) [\|P_{N^c} V x\| + \|P_{M^c} x\|] = \left(1 + \frac{1}{1 - \|P_N V P_M\|}\right) [\|x\|_{N^c,g} + \|P_{M^c} x\|] \\ &= \left(1 + \frac{1}{1 - \|P_N V P_M\|}\right) \left[\left(\sum_{j \in M^c} |f_j(x)|^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} + \left(\sum_{k \in N^c} |g_k(x)|^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \right]. \end{aligned}$$

For $x \in \mathcal{X}$, we now find

$$\begin{aligned}
 \|P_N V P_M x\|^p &= \left\| \sum_{k \in N} f_k(V P_M x) \tau_k \right\|^p = \left(\sum_{k \in N} |f_k(V P_M x)|^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} = \sum_{k \in N} \left| (f_k V) \left(\sum_{j \in M} f_j(x) \tau_j \right) \right|^p \\
 &= \sum_{k \in N} \left| \sum_{j \in M} f_j(x) f_k(V \tau_j) \right|^p = \sum_{k \in N} \left| \sum_{j \in M} f_j(x) f_k \left(\sum_{r=1}^{\infty} g_r(\tau_j) \tau_r \right) \right|^p = \sum_{k \in N} \left| \sum_{j \in M} f_j(x) \sum_{r=1}^{\infty} g_r(\tau_j) f_k(\tau_r) \right|^p \\
 &= \sum_{k \in N} \left| \sum_{j \in M} f_j(x) g_k(\tau_j) \right|^p \leq \sum_{k \in N} \left(\sum_{j \in M} |f_j(x) g_k(\tau_j)| \right)^p \leq \left(\sup_{j, k \in \mathbb{N}} |g_k(\tau_j)| \right)^p \sum_{k \in N} \left(\sum_{j \in M} |f_j(x)| \right)^p \\
 &= \left(\sup_{j, k \in \mathbb{N}} |g_k(\tau_j)| \right)^p o(N) \left(\sum_{j \in M} |f_j(x)| \right)^p \leq \left(\sup_{j, k \in \mathbb{N}} |g_k(\tau_j)| \right)^p o(N) \left(\sum_{j \in M} |f_j(x)|^p \right)^{\frac{p}{p}} \left(\sum_{j \in M} 1^q \right)^{\frac{p}{q}} \\
 &\leq \left(\sup_{j, k \in \mathbb{N}} |g_k(\tau_j)| \right)^p o(N) \left(\sum_{j=1}^{\infty} |f_j(x)|^p \right)^{\frac{p}{p}} \left(\sum_{j \in M} 1^q \right)^{\frac{p}{q}} = \left(\sup_{j, k \in \mathbb{N}} |g_k(\tau_j)| \right)^p o(N) \|x\|^p o(M)^{\frac{p}{q}}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore

$$\|P_N V P_M\| \leq \sup_{j, k \in \mathbb{N}} |g_k(\tau_j)| o(N)^{\frac{1}{p}} o(M)^{\frac{1}{q}}.$$

□

By interchanging p-orthonormal bases in Theorem 2.5 we get the following theorem.

Theorem 2.6. *Let $(\{f_j\}_{j=1}^{\infty}, \{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^{\infty})$ and $(\{g_k\}_{k=1}^{\infty}, \{\omega_k\}_{k=1}^{\infty})$ be p-orthonormal bases for \mathcal{X} . If $M, N \subseteq \mathbb{N}$ are such that*

$$o(M)^{\frac{1}{q}} o(N)^{\frac{1}{p}} < \frac{1}{\sup_{j, k \in \mathbb{N}} |f_j(\omega_k)|},$$

then for all $x \in \mathcal{X}$,

$$\|x\| \leq \left(1 + \frac{1}{1 - o(M)^{\frac{1}{q}} o(N)^{\frac{1}{p}} \sup_{j, k \in \mathbb{N}} |f_j(\omega_k)|} \right) \left[\left(\sum_{k \in M^c} |g_k(x)|^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} + \left(\sum_{j \in N^c} |f_j(x)|^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \right].$$

In particular, if x is supported on M in the expansion using Schauder basis $\{\omega_k\}_{k=1}^{\infty}$ and x is supported on N in the expansion using Schauder basis $\{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^{\infty}$, then $x = 0$.

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